

Jan (samba season). Samba rice is always less productive because of cold weather coupled with pests and diseases. A medium to fine rice grain type is preferred by farmers.

Breeding line P.837, a derivative of the cross IR8/H.4, appears promising for this area. It matures in 145-150 d. Grains are medium slender and translucent. Yields average 5.8 t/ha, an increase of 29, 22, and 23% over IR20, Co 43, and Mahsuri puthae (white ponni), respectively.

P.837 has recorded resistance to such major pests as brown planthopper and leaffolder. It was tolerant of the major diseases blast and helminthosporium (see table). □

Field reaction^a of P.837 to major insects and diseases, compared to check varieties. Pondicherry, India, 1984-87.

Variety	Insects			Diseases		
	BPH	Leaffolder	Stem borer (%)	Blast	Helminthosporium	Sheath rot
				<i>1984-85</i>		
P.837	3	3	8.5	1	3	3
IR20	9	3	14.0	1	7	5
				<i>1985-86</i>		
P.837	3	3	9.0	3	3	1
IR20	7	5	18.5	5	7	3
Co 43	5	7	16.0	5	5	7
				<i>1986-87</i>		
P.837	—	—	10.2	—	3	5
IR20	—	5	16.0	—	7	7
Co 43	—	7	16.5	—	3	7
Co 1009	—	5	14.5	—	5	5

^aStandard evaluation system for rice.

Gall midge (GM)-resistant rice cultivars

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So far three varieties resistant to GM—Kakatiya, Surekha, and Pothana—have been released for general cultivation. Cultivars suited to different cropping practices and with improved grain type also are needed.

One local practice is sowing rice under dry conditions and converting to irrigation when water is available in tanks. Two short-duration, GM-resistant varieties—WGL 18011(CR44/W.12708) and WGL 20471-97 (BC.5/W.12708)—were sown in the 1987 wet season (WS) using the local seed drill at 30-cm spacing in 73.2 m² plot. This dry condition was converted to wet conditions at 40 d.

Both varieties matured in 100 d and yielded 3.0 t/ha. They have long slender grains. In minikit tests in the dry season (DS), WGL 20471-97 averaged 6.3 t yield/ha, 47% higher than Tella Hamsa. Both varieties are suitable for late, direct sowing.

Two GM-resistant cultures—WGL 44645 and WGL 48684—have superior grain quality. WGL 44645 (WGL 23022/Surekha) has a 125 d duration in

WS and 135 d in DS. It has stiff straw and long slender grains. Grain quality is superior to that of varieties released earlier. In minikit trials, it yielded 4.2 t/ha against 2.8 t/ha for Tella Hamsa. It is tolerant of stem borer and hispa.

WGL 48684 (WGL 27120/(Mashuri/WGL 17672)/Surekha) has a 135 d duration in WS. Grains are medium slender. It is also suitable for DS provided sowing is before December.

Both varieties have 9% protein content. □

TR-RNR-21, a new medium-duration rice variety, released in Andhra Pradesh (A.P.)

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TR-RNR-21 is a derivative of the cross IR8/TR-5. TR-5 is a N_f-induced dwarf mutant of salinity-resistant SR-26-B.

In initial yield evaluations in 1972-78, it gave 54% higher yields than Jaya in the wet season and 19% in the dry

season and compared favorably with IR8 and Sona.

Compared with Pankaj, Jaya, RP-4-14, Sona, Surekha, RNR-32341, and Prabhat, in 1975-80 trials, TR-RNR-21 gave average yields 10.1% higher than those of the highest yielding checks and 19.8% higher than the average of 7 checks (see table). In minikit trials at more than 90 sites in 9 districts of Telangana region, mean grain yield (3.8 t/ha) was 19% higher than yield of local checks. TR-RNR-21 was released in 1987 as Hari, for general cultivation

Relative yield performance of TR-RNR-21 (Hari) at Andhra Pradesh Agriculture University and in the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad, India.

Variety	Mean yield (t/ha)		
	Monsoon season (5 trials)	Dry season (6 trials)	Total
TR-RNR-21 (<i>Hari</i>)	5.4	6.3	5.9
Highest yielding check	4.9	5.8	5.4
All checks combined	4.7	5.1	4.9

under irrigated transplanted conditions in Telangana region, A.P. (except in the endemic gall midge-prone areas).

Hari is characterized as follows: medium duration (135-140 d); semidwarf (93 cm); erect, compact, and nonlodging with dark green foliage; no anthocyanin pigment; long (10.14 mm)

slender grain with a kernel length (7.35 mm):breadth (2.08 mm) ratio of 3.54; flinty, white, translucent, nonglutinous grain; no white belly; 1,000-grain weight 25.2 g; protein content, 7.14%; hulling, milling, and head rice recovery, 80, 74.5, and 68%, respectively; good cooking quality. It is tolerant of blast, tungro

virus, sheath blight, and brown leaf spot diseases and green leafhopper, leafhopper, and stem borers. A distinguishing characteristic is a long flag leaf that grows far above the panicle and remains green even after maturity. □

MW10, a promising short-duration variety for western West Bengal

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Purulia, Bankura, and Western Midnapur districts of West Bengal are mostly rainfed rice monocropped Jul-Oct (kharif). In spite of average annual rains, extended breaks in rainfall often occur at critical growth stages. Acute water stress significantly reduces rice yields on lateritic soils with high infiltration in an undulated terrain. The problem becomes severe when

Average yield and some agronomic characteristics of MW-10 and other rice varieties in on-farm trials, West Bengal, India.

Variety	Effective tillers/hill (no.)	Grains (no./panicle)	Duration (d)	Av grain yield (t/ha)	AV yield/d (kg/ha)
MW10	13	103	100	2.8	28.0
IET1444	9	110	117	2.5	21.2
Palman 579	8	125	120	2.8	23.6
IR36	12	99	122	2.9	23.8
CR126-42-1	9	93	105	2.8	26.5
IR50	18	104	110	2.1	19.3
IET2815	10	124	114	2.7	23.6
LSD (P=0.05)	2.7	18	6	0.2	1.5

transplanting is late.

We evaluated the promising new variety MW10 against six short-duration transplanted varieties, including locally grown Palman 579, IR36, and IET1444, in six farmers' field trials, in a

randomized block design with four replications. MW10 performed consistently better than the other varieties (see table). Its short duration allows a following short-duration pulse or oilseed crop. □

Improved rice varieties released in North Central Thailand

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Two PSL breeding lines—Phitsanulok 60-1 (PSL 60-1) and Phitsanulok 60-2 (PSL 60-2)—were released in 1987.

PSL 60-1, a high-yielding, photoperiod-sensitive variety is from a three-way cross among Khao Dawk Mali 105, Nahng Mon S-4, and IR26 (KDML 105/NM S-4//IR26). The cultivar is tall with long, slender, clear grain, low amylose content, and good cooking quality. During 1981-85, it averaged 3.48 t/ha, 12% higher than KDML 105, a standard variety (Table 1). It is moderately resistant to bacterial blight, sheath rot, ragged stunt virus,

Table 1. Grain yield and quality of PSL 60-1 and PSL 60-2. Phitsanulok, Thailand, 1987.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)	% increase over check	Grain characteristic					
			Length (mm)	Chalkiness (%)	Amylose (%)	GC ^a	GT ^b	ER ^c
PSL 60-1	3.48	12	7.30	0.24	17.1	S	L	1.64
KDML 105	3.12	—	7.46	0.31	13.7	S	L	1.70
PSL 60-2	4.73	17	7.30	0.98	29.6	H	I/L	1.58
RD 1	4.05	—	7.34	1.05	30.0	H	L	1.70

^a Gel consistency. S = soft, H = hard. By the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES). ^b Gel temperature. L = low, I = intermediate. By SES. ^c Elongation ratio (the ratio of the length of cooked rice to raw rice).

Table 2. Reaction of PSL 60-1 and 60-2 to diseases and insects.^a Phitsanulok, Thailand, 1987.

Variety	Reaction ^b to									
	BI	BB	ShB	ShR	YOLV	RSV	GLH	BPH	WBPH	GM
PSL 60-1	S	MR	MS	MR	VS	MR	MS	MR	MS	MR
KDML 105	S	S	MR	MR	VS	S	MS	S	MS	S
PSL 60-2	MR	MR	MS	R	MS	MS	MS	MR	MS	—
RD1	MS	S	MS	—	S	VS	MS	S	MS	—

^a BI = blast, BB = bacterial blight, ShB = sheath blight, YOLV = yellow orange leaf virus, RSV = ragged stunt, GLH = green leafhopper, BPH = brown planthopper, WBPH = whitebacked planthopper, GM = gall midge. ^b By SES: VS = very susceptible, S = susceptible, MS = moderately susceptible, MR = moderately resistant, R = resistant.